

POLITICAL SKILLS OF SCHOOL HEADS AND SCHOOL WORK ATMOSPHERE

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Abstract: This study is aimed to find out the relationship between political skills of school head and school work atmosphere. This study utilized the non-experimental quantitative research design using descriptive technique involving teachers in Davao Occidental Division, Philippines. The study was conducted on the second semester of School Year 2025-2026. Research instruments on political skills of school head and school work atmosphere were used as source of data. Using mean and pearson-r as statistical tools to treat the data, the study showed the following results: the study found to exhibit a high level of political skills of school head. This means that the provisions relating to political skills of school head is oftentimes observed. The study revealed a high level of school work atmosphere. This indicates that the provisions relating to school work atmosphere are embodied in the item is oftentimes observed. The results of the study also confirm that there is a significant relationship between political skills of school head and school work atmosphere. This implies that the higher the political skills of school head, the higher is the school work atmosphere. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between political skills of school head and school work atmosphere was rejected.

Keywords: Political skills of school head, school work atmosphere, school administration and supervision, quantitative research.

I. INTRODUCTION

The school work atmosphere refers to the overall climate or environment in which teachers, staff, and students operate daily. It includes the quality of relationships among colleagues, communication with leadership, levels of collaboration, workload expectations, and emotional well-being within the school community. A healthy and positive school work atmosphere promotes job satisfaction, motivation, and productivity among teachers, ultimately leading to better learning outcomes for students (Tilkioğlu & Bülbül, 2024).

However, in many schools today, there is a growing problem of poor or deteriorating work atmosphere, which is affecting both teacher performance and student achievement. A research from Institute of Education reveals that teachers in England have among the lowest job satisfaction levels, even when compared to 22 other countries. This is mainly due to the fact that they overwhelming workload and poor work-life balance. Teachers work an average of 51–52 hours per week, significantly higher than comparable professions. Much of this time is spent on non-teaching tasks like marking, admin, and behavior management (Aldrich & Woodin, 2021).

In the Philippines, issues on school work atmosphere is depicted by a number of core challenges in school work environment which is characterized by overburdened teachers and role overload. Notably, 1 in 4 teachers (27%) work more than 60 hours

weekly; only 45% of teachers' work time is spent engaging in classroom teaching (23.4 hours/week) while the remaining 55% (28.6 hours/week) is taken up by ancillary teaching-related tasks such as lesson prep, grading, and assessments, about 34% or 3.6 hours/day (Gonzales, Guimary & Gabunilas, 2022).

In other parts of the country, the school work atmosphere is observed through resource deficiencies and climate stressors. The central schools face infrastructure neglect, overcrowded classrooms, shortages in classrooms, resources, and school health facilities. In Metro Manila's Northern Manila District, up to 90% of elementary students attend schools with severely congested classrooms, defined as having a student-to-classroom ratio of at least 50:1. Similar high congestion appears in Southern (76.8%) and Eastern (60.1%) Manila districts, as well as in nearby provinces like Rizal (66%) and Cavite (57.7%). In some cases, many schools doubling as evacuation centers during natural disasters, all compounded by extreme heat and climate-related disruptions (Alviola, 2025).

In the local setting, one of the main issues contributing to a negative school work atmosphere is excessive workload and unrealistic expectations placed on teachers. Many educators face pressure to meet curriculum standards, complete administrative tasks, manage student behavior, and adapt to continuous changes in teaching methods and technologies, all while receiving limited support. This overload often results in stress, burnout, and a loss of motivation, making it difficult for teachers to maintain energy and enthusiasm in the classroom.

Although school work atmosphere problems come in different forms and size, the school head can help teacher alleviate its impact to teachers through manifesting a strong political skills. Hence, this study seeks to underscore the relationship between political skills of school heads and school work atmosphere to ascertain the relationship between the two variables. Today, the researcher has rarely come across with a study on the study regarding these two variables. It is in this context that the researcher prompted to conduct this study to address population gap.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE

Statement of the Problem

This study is aimed to find out the relationship between political skills of school heads and school work atmosphere. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following objectives:

1. What is the level of political skills of school heads in terms of:
 - 1.1 Social Astuteness;
 - 1.2 Interpersonal Influence;
 - 1.3 Networking Ability;
 - 1.4 Apparent Sincerity, and
 - 1.5 Charisma?
2. What is the level of school work atmosphere in terms of:
 - 2.1 Managing Change;
 - 2.2 Achieving Goals;
 - 2.3 Coordinated Team-work;
 - 2.4 Customer Orientation, and
 - 2.5 Cultural Strength?
3. Is there a significant relationship between political skills of school heads and school work atmosphere?

Hypothesis

Ho1. There is no significant relationship between political skills of school heads and school work atmosphere.

III. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study will adopt a quantitative correlational research design to examine the relationship between teachers' digital transformation skills and students' internal drive aptitude. The quantitative approach allows for statistical analysis of the strength and direction of associations between variables, providing empirical evidence on how teacher competencies in digital technology influence students' motivation and learning behavior.

Non-experimental correlational research is a research design used to determine whether and to what degree a relationship exists between two or more quantifiable variables, without establishing cause and effect in which in this study, it will look into the relationship political skills of school heads and school work atmosphere.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tools were used in the analysis of data.

Mean. This will be used to determine the level of political skills of school heads and school work atmosphere.

Pearson *r*. This will be used to determine the significance of the relationship between political skills of school heads and school work atmosphere.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Political Skills of School Head

Shown in Table 1 is the level of political skills of school head with an overall mean of 4.14 with a descriptive equivalent of high indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes observed. The overall mean was the result obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which was appended in this study.

Table 1. Political Skills of School Head

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Levels
Social Astuteness	4.15	High
Interpersonal Influence	4.16	High
Networking Ability	4.13	High
Apparent Sincerity	4.11	High
Charisma	4.17	High
Overall	4.14	High

Among the enumerated indicators, charisma has the highest mean rating with a mean score of 4.17 or high, interpersonal influence, 4.16 or high, social astuteness, 4.15 or high, networking ability, 4.13 or high, and apparent sincerity, 4.11 or high.

The result of the study is in line with the statement of Valmores (2021) who establishes that political skills of a school head refer to the ability of school leaders to effectively understand, influence, and manage relationships within the school and the broader educational community in order to achieve organizational goals. These skills involve navigating complex social environments, building alliances, and maintaining positive relationships with teachers, staff, parents, community members, and education authorities.

The result of the study corroborates the statement of Dellomas & Deri (2022) who demonstrates that one important aspect of political skills is social awareness and relationship building. School heads must understand the perspectives, needs, and interests of different individuals and groups within the school community. By demonstrating empathy, respect, and good communication, they can establish trust and credibility. This helps them gain support for school initiatives, encourage collaboration among staff members, and maintain a positive and inclusive school climate.

Level of School Work Atmosphere

Shown in Table 2 is the level of school work atmosphere with an overall mean of 4.11 with a descriptive equivalent of high indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes observed. The overall mean was the result obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which was appended in this study.

Table 2. School Work Atmosphere

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Levels
Managing Change	4.09	High
Achieving Goals	4.07	High
Coordinated Team-work	4.13	High
Customer Orientation	4.11	High
Cultural Strength	4.10	High
Overall	4.10	High

Among the enumerated indicators, coordinated team-work the highest mean rating with a mean score of 4.13 or high, customer orientation, 4.11 or high, cultural strength, 4.10 or high, managing change, 4.09 or high, and achieving goals, 4.07 or high. The result of the study corresponds with the statement of Hai, Bao, Wang, Zhang & Shu (2024) school work atmosphere refers to the overall environment and conditions in which teachers, staff, and administrators perform their duties within a school. It includes the quality of relationships among staff members, leadership practices, communication patterns, and the level of support provided within the workplace. A positive school work atmosphere promotes cooperation, respect, trust, and motivation among teachers and staff, which contributes to effective teaching and learning.

The result of the study is consistent with the statement of Stepanović & Medenica (2025) who demonstrates that a healthy school work atmosphere is characterized by open communication, collaboration, and supportive leadership. When teachers feel respected and valued by school leaders and colleagues, they are more likely to share ideas, work together on projects, and participate actively in school activities. Such an environment encourages professional growth, innovation, and a strong sense of belonging among staff members.

Significance on the Relationship between Political Skills of School Head and School Work Atmosphere

Illustrated in Table 3 were the results of the test of relationship between variables involved in the study. The overall correlation had a computed value of 0.608 with a probability value of $p < 0.01$ which is significant at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between political skills of school head and school work atmosphere is rejected.

The result of the study reflects the statement of Gamala & Marpa (2022) who indicates that The relationship between the political skills of a school head and school work atmosphere highlights how the leader's ability to navigate social dynamics, influence others, and build networks directly impacts the environment in which teachers and staff operate. Political skills, such as social astuteness, interpersonal influence, networking ability, apparent sincerity, and charisma, enable school heads to manage relationships, resolve conflicts, and motivate staff, all of which contribute to a positive, productive, and collaborative work atmosphere.

The result of the study confirms the statement of Bastasa & Guhao Jr (2024) who reports that when school heads demonstrate strong political skills, they can foster trust, cooperation, and open communication among teachers and staff. Social astuteness allows leaders to understand staff concerns and anticipate reactions to changes, while interpersonal influence helps them guide behavior and encourage participation in school initiatives. Networking ability connects the school to external resources and support systems, enhancing collaboration and morale. Apparent sincerity and charisma further strengthen staff confidence in leadership, encouraging engagement and commitment. Together, these skills create a work atmosphere characterized by teamwork, motivation, and alignment with school goals.

The result of the study is in line with the statement of Özdemir (2021) who emphasizes that a positive school work atmosphere influenced by political skills supports organizational performance and teacher satisfaction. Staff in such an

environment are more likely to embrace change, work collaboratively, and focus on achieving both individual and collective objectives. Conversely, a school head lacking political skills may struggle to build trust, resolve conflicts, or motivate staff, leading to a negative work atmosphere, reduced collaboration, and lower productivity. Therefore, the political skills of a school head play a critical role in shaping a school's work environment, affecting both staff morale and overall school effectiveness.

Table 3. Significance on the Relationship between Political Skills of School Head and School Work Atmosphere

Pair	Variables	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Decision on Ho
IV and DV	Political Skills of School Head and School Work Atmosphere	0.608	0.000	Reject

V. CONCLUSION

Based from the findings of the study, conclusions are drawn in this section. The study found to exhibit a high level of political skills of school head. This means that the provisions relating to political skills of school head is oftentimes observed.

The study revealed a high level of school work atmosphere. This indicates that the provisions relating to school work atmosphere are embodied in the item is oftentimes observed.

The results of the study also confirm that there is a significant relationship between political skills of school head and school work atmosphere. This implies that the higher the political skills of school head, the higher is the school work atmosphere. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between political skills of school head and school work atmosphere was rejected.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

The study revealed a high level of school work atmosphere. The researcher recommends that the school head may improve in the area of apparent sincerity as this has the lowest mean rating among all the indicators. The researcher recommends that principals may demonstrate sincerity in communication and actions by always aligning words with your actions to build trust and credibility among teachers, staff, students, and stakeholders; show genuine interest in others by listening actively during conversations, ask meaningful questions, and recognize the contributions of individuals; communicate authentically by avoiding superficial or insincere remarks; focus on meaningful engagement that fosters trust and collaboration; develop and share a clear vision by regularly articulating vision for the school's future in ways that are inspiring, practical, and aligned with the school's mission and goals, and provide inspiring strategic and organizational goals by communicating how each goal contributes to the broader vision, emphasizing its importance for student success and organizational growth.

The study revealed a high level of school work atmosphere. The researcher recommends that the school teachers and school heads improve in the area of achieving goals as this has the lowest mean among all the indicators. They may clarify and align goals by ensuring that personal and team goals are clearly defined and directly connected to the school's mission and educational objectives; embrace challenging but attainable goals by viewing ambitious goals as opportunities for growth rather than obstacles; focus on measurable outcomes and accountability by tracing progress toward goals using measurable indicators such as student performance, project completion, or team collaboration; participate actively in goal-setting by engaging in discussions with colleagues and supervisors to help define team and individual goals, and commit to continuous improvement by regularly stretching goals to push for higher performance, innovation, and skill development.

The results of the study also confirm that there is a significant relationship between political skills of school head and school work atmosphere. The researcher recommends that teachers may build trust and collaboration by actively engaging with school leaders by communicating openly, providing constructive feedback, and participating in collaborative decision-making. this supports a positive school work atmosphere; support leadership initiatives by recognizing the role of school heads' political skills in shaping the school environment and cooperate in implementing programs, policies, and innovations, and develop interpersonal skills by strengthening own communication, teamwork, and conflict-resolution skills to contribute positively to a harmonious and productive work atmosphere.

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School principals may enhance political skills by focusing on improving key political skills such as social astuteness, interpersonal influence, networking ability, apparent sincerity, and charisma to foster trust, collaboration, and engagement among teachers and staff; model positive leadership behaviors by demonstrating transparency, fairness, and empathy in interactions, encouraging a supportive and motivating school work atmosphere, and facilitate team cohesion by using influence to build strong relationships among staff, resolve conflicts effectively, and promote shared goals, collaboration, and commitment to the school's mission.

District supervisors may provide leadership development by offering professional development programs and workshops to strengthen school heads' political and interpersonal skills; monitor school climate by supporting schools in assessing and improving their work atmosphere by providing guidance, feedback, and resources that promote positive relationships and collaboration, and encourage best practices by facilitating the sharing of successful leadership strategies among principals and schools to enhance political skill application and create supportive, productive work environments.

The researcher also recommends to future researchers to conduct similar study and explore some indicators that are not included in this study in another setting in order to uncover new knowledge relevant to the topics presented in this study.

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